

Music as a pedagogical intervention strategy for children with attention deficit and hyperactivity disorders in the second grade of the José Joaquín Flórez Hernández School, Ibagué, Colombia

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The classroom is a space for the integral formation of children at an early age; therefore, it must be a safe environment that fosters the growth of students in a comprehensive manner. This is especially necessary in the case of students who have particular requirements, such as attention deficit hyperactivity disorder ADHD, who present symptoms with wide repercussions on their academic performance and with direct incidence in events such as school dropout and other long-term problems. In this study, a pedagogical strategy was designed and implemented for students with ADHD, who are in the second grade at the José Joaquín Flórez Hernández School, San Francisco Club, in the city of Ibagué, Colombia. Among the results, it was found that musical intervention has a positive impact on aspects such as memory, concentration, self-esteem, self-control, and healthy interpersonal relationships of the children who participated, thus corroborating, on the one hand, the premise that music is a tool to help children with ADHD from the classroom, as an adjuvant to traditional pharmacological treatments and, on the other hand, demonstrating the role of teachers as active players in social development and health from education.

Keywords: Music, attention deficit, hyperactivity, Teaching-Learning.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Among the different approaches and pedagogical approaches to the treatment of symptoms of behavioral and learning disorders, such as ADHD, interventions that include the use of the arts, especially music, have been shown to have a positive impact on their effects on school-age children. However, in the regional context, information on this type of intervention has been precarious, despite the need to attend to the particularities of each student concerning his or her pace and learning style in line with respect for plurality, on the one hand, and, on the other, to make the learning space in the classroom enjoyable.

Accordingly, music has been presented as a valuable and complementary tool to address the difficulties associated with ADHD, since pedagogical interventions that incorporate it have shown positive impacts on its symptoms, but its application in the regional context has been limited.

The latter is relevant to the extent that if properly addressed, it can improve learning processes in children and adolescents of children and adolescents; In this regard, it should be noted that, in Colombia, about 15% of children have learning difficulties [1], a situation that becomes even more complex in situations of ADHD, which underlines the importance of addressing this disorder comprehensively, considering not only pharmacological management but also pedagogical approaches [2], which address the specific needs of students with limitations for inclusion in the educational system, especially in low socioeconomic contexts, for whom the situation becomes more complex.

Specifically, in the evaluated educational institution, José Joaquín Flórez Hernández San Francisco Club, a public entity in Ibagué, Colombia, a group of second-grade students was identified with characteristics that indicate possible difficulties related to ADHD, which affect not only their academic performance but also the overall learning environment, causing additional disciplinary challenges and disrupting classroom dynamics.

This research is based on the urgent need to address the learning difficulties of children with ADHD through an artistic language, such as music, to avoid the risk of dropping out of school and, at the same time, to promote solid foundations for their academic future. In this regard, the lack of institutional attention and effective pedagogical strategies in the local context for this population is striking, highlighting the importance of exploring new interventions from the educational field.

Thus, [3] argues that music not only facilitates the acquisition of new knowledge but also improves children's cognitive skills, influencing their understanding and comprehension. Likewise, [4] explores the application of music as a treatment for hyperactive children, focusing on phonological processing and early reading. On this topic, the literature reviewed points out the positive impact of music on learning and reading skills, as evidenced by pedagogical experiences in Costa Rica [5].

Promptly, [6] addresses *music* education and emphasizes how it affects cognitive, physical, and socio-affective areas, highlighting its influence on student motivation and interest. Similarly, [7] explores the interdisciplinary nature of music in primary education, emphasizing its ability to motivate students before daily reading, with a special benefit for children with specific educational needs.

Additionally, [8] evidences the positive influence of artistic interventions, specifically plastic arts, on neuropsychological mechanisms in children, highlighting favorable changes in school actions. In line with the above, [9] proposes practices based on song recreation and improvisation to strengthen phonological awareness in early childhood children, while [10] seeks to understand the experience of teachers using technological mediations for students with mild intellectual disabilities.

At the local level, there are few studies on this topic; however, there are some outstanding works such as that of [11], who proposes children's music as a motivating agent for the integral development of preschool children; on the other hand, [12] highlights the importance of play and music to minimize scattered attention in transitional children. Continuing with this review, [13] suggests implementing graphic-plastic techniques to strengthen reading processes in preschool, and [14] adopts Dalcrozian rhythmic to improve attention and memory in third-grade children, showing improvements in areas such as selective attention and echoic memory.

Recapitulating the above, the research question arises: what positive changes does the implementation of a pedagogical strategy based on children's music generate in children with learning difficulties related to ADHD in the second grade of the educational institution Joaquín Flórez, San Francisco Club, in the city of Ibagué? Based on this question, the objective is to design and implement a pedagogical strategy based on music for children with attention disorders and hyperactivity in the second grade of the I.E. José Joaquín Flórez Hernández.

2. METHOD

To fulfill the objective of this project, a methodological design was proposed in which music is integrated into the academic environment as a tool to strengthen aspects involved in learning to read, thus establishing the possible effects (negative or positive) on the population to be evaluated. For this, the present research is framed in the socio-critical paradigm, since it places the teacher as a researcher and, at the same time, as a promoter of changes by addressing problems close to the educational practice in the classroom, through a qualitative paradigm and under a methodological design of action-research type.

The sample of this research includes nine students, between 7 and 8 years old, who have been previously characterized with learning difficulties related to attention deficit and hyperactivity disorders using an evaluation test. These students are part of the second grade of the public educational institution José Joaquín Flórez Hernández, San Francisco Club, in Ibagué, Colombia.

2.1 Pedagogical and specialized diagnostic test

A diagnostic test was conducted using the online questionnaire platform, consisting of 30 questions, 17 corresponding to language and 13 to mathematics. It should be noted that the first two questions of the language test were carried out jointly with the teacher. Each of the questions included in its structure the basic learning rights DBA for first grade, as a requirement for second grade, these results were interpreted through statistical indexes guided according to the Program for the Transformation of Educational Quality.

Then, based on the results obtained through the pedagogical diagnostic test, we continued with the specialized diagnosis, if pertinent, which consisted of accompaniment by child psychology, to evaluate and describe the presence of attentional difficulties or hyperactivity; this after obtaining due authorization from the person responsible for each student (parent or guardian).

2.2 Proposal for musical-pedagogical intervention

This study proposed a series of 16 activities, detailed in Table 1, framed in the workshop model, for the pedagogical intervention of the aforementioned population; the elaboration of these proposals involved a diagnostic evaluation of the student's strengths and weaknesses in the areas of mathematics, language and reading comprehension, based on the diagnostic test called *Carlos and Marcela* [15].

Table 1. Activities developed in the intervention: *All my attention on the song: Musical workshop at school.*

Activity	Duration (min)	The objective of the activity
1	15	To strengthen the attentional skills of children with hyperactivity in second grade.
2		Perform percussion sequences with their bodies to strengthen the children's attention, memory, and group work skills.
3		To strengthen the attentional emotion and impulsivity control abilities of children with second-grade hyperactivity.
4		To strengthen the attentional skills of children with hyperactivity in second grade.
5		To strengthen the attentional skills of children with hyperactivity in second grade.
6		To strengthen the attentional and memory skills of children with hyperactivity in second grade.
7		To strengthen the attentional and memory skills of children with hyperactivity in second grade.
8		To strengthen the attentional and memory skills of children with hyperactivity in second grade.
9		To strengthen the attentional and memory skills of children with hyperactivity in second grade.
10		To strengthen the attentional skills of children with hyperactivity in second grade.
11		To strengthen the attentional and motor skills of children with hyperactivity in second grade.
12		To stimulate attention, concentration, memory, and interpersonal relationships in children with second-grade hyperactivity.

13		To stimulate attention, concentration, memory, and interpersonal relationships in children with grade 2 hyperactivity.
14	30	To stimulate attention, concentration, memory, and interpersonal relationships in children with second-grade hyperactivity.
15		To stimulate attention, concentration, memory, and interpersonal relationships in children with grade 2 hyperactivity.
16	20	To stimulate attention and concentration in children with grade 2 hyperactivity.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Pedagogical and Psychological Diagnostic Test

As for the results obtained, in general, the students satisfactorily completed the diagnostic test for second grade, demonstrating the presence of an adequate level of reading comprehension, mathematical skills, and problem-solving, which is why the specialized diagnostic process continued, with the results shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Percentage of approval per question

As illustrated, 19 questions were answered correctly by 100% of the students evaluated, and only two were answered incorrectly by about half of them. Based on the teacher's observation of disciplinary and school performance problems in several second-grade students, we proceeded to investigate the cause, initially finding that they met the requirements in the area of language and mathematics expected for the second grade, presenting an adequate level of reading comprehension, mathematical skills, and problem-solving. In line with this, we continued with a process directed by a professional child psychologist to determine the possible presence of problems related to attention or hyperactivity as a cause of the deficiencies.

In line with what was stated by [16], properly trained education professionals can exercise active vigilance on the warning signs related to attention disorders, such as ADHD. In addition, it should be emphasized that educational work should take place in cross-cutting conditions so that the support of professionals from other areas allows the urgent attention required by students with particular conditions for development and thus achieve success in their academic activities, and disciplinary behavior according to the circumstances.

This will have repercussions on social aspects in addition to education, as is the case of public health, given the number of pharmacological treatments that are carried out in hospitals to treat attention disorders, which could be treated in an alternative or complementary manner without the risks that the continuous and long-term intake of pharmacological drugs may entail, since, as [17] reminds us: *the continuous administration of psychotropic drugs in no way guarantees stable therapeutic effects, while the doubt persists about their potential negative consequences on a brain in formation.*

Now, ADHD is one of the most common psychiatric diagnoses in childhood, with an estimated prevalence of 5% in school-aged children [18], characterized mainly by difficulties in maintaining attention, hyperactivity, and impulsivity, which cause behavioral problems and poor academic performance [19]. When relatives of children with ADHD were asked about the impairments and disabilities that may be associated with the disorder, they reported that it has multiple negative impacts on schooling, daily life, social exchange, and family relationships, in addition to notoriously negatively affecting self-esteem.

Precisely, this situation was identified in several second-grade students of the educational institution José Joaquín Flórez Hernández, who presented behavioral and academic performance alterations that, after standardized tests and processes, were diagnosed as ADHD. Although the treatment usually indicated for this disorder in children is pharmacological or through clinical therapeutic processes, for some time now the importance of a holistic approach that includes the arts and, especially, music, has been proposed to optimize the quality of life and meet the physical, emotional, mental, social and cognitive needs of children.

Through this approach (known as music therapy) a non-invasive therapy is offered to access the nervous system and promote brain changes that translate into behavioral, learning, emotional, and social improvements. Among the benefits in the literature are the reduction of anxiety and stress, an improvement in communication and expression of emotions, as well as in social skills, in addition to the improvement in memory and cognitive functions, and its coadjuvant character in medical treatments for psychological and psychiatric disorders [20-22].

Based on the above premises, in the case of the present research, we proceeded to design, structure, and implement a pedagogical intervention strategy based on music for children with ADHD in the second grade of the Educational Institution, which was implemented both for them and for their classmates who do not experience this disorder, finding, after the evaluation, positive results, both in their disciplinary behavior and in their overall school performance, which is consistent with what has been raised in the state of the art, for example in the case of [23].

According to studies conducted on music therapy, it can be affirmed that it generates significant short-term effects on the development of communication and social interaction [23]. Likewise, [23] finds that the therapy speeds up neuronal synapses, making adaptive responses both better and faster, and ultimately producing an improvement in self-esteem, communication, adaptation, and socialization in the environment, as well as better motor development and an increase in attention span.

The results found after the evaluation of the activities proposed and executed in the strategy showed improvements, both cognitive and behavioral, in the population under study, which were manifested in the form of increased attention, concentration, and participation, thus supporting the use of music as a suitable adjuvant tool in the management of ADHD symptoms, as already indicated by authors such as [4, 24, 25], among others.

Likewise, the results obtained support specific hypotheses and theories about the mechanisms of action of music on the brain and its relationship with neurobiological alterations, as in the case of ADHD; Thus, the behavioral and cognitive improvements observed after the implementation of the music therapy program were evident in the areas that presented deficits, such as attention, concentration, impulse control and social skills, allowing the children to improve their concentration and focus, which, in turn, resulted in greater participation and integration, and gave them greater self-esteem.

The scientific evidence supported by praxis, as is the case of the present work, indicates then in a majority and conclusive manner that music seems to compensate for the deficiencies in brain functioning related to ADHD, by promoting positive changes in the neural substrates involved, as indicated by [17, 26] after neuroimaging research, concluding that music not only activates the auditory areas of the brain, but also recruits a distributed network of limbic and cortical regions related to cognitive and emotional functions.

Recent studies, that have evaluated the effects of music therapy using functional magnetic resonance imaging, have found increases in blood flow, connectivity, and electrophysiological activity between frontal, limbic, and basal ganglia areas after musical interventions, changes that have been associated with behavioral and clinical improvements [17, 27].

Current evidence suggests that rhythmic, melodic, and harmonic stimuli coordinated in music therapy, singing, and instrumental performance, activate and reinforce brain circuits involved in cognitive and behavioral processes, which present functional and structural deficits in children with ADHD. The above was evidenced in the case of the present research through the 16 activities in which sound, rhythm and harmony,

singing and music, action and movement were combined, giving rise to creative expression combined with playfulness.

Precisely, the literature also mentions the beneficial effects resulting from incorporating musical activities in educational contexts [28-30], observing an increase in student motivation and participation, which coincides with the results of the present research. On this subject [30] argues that, just as there are factors that favor attention levels, there are others that interfere with and hinder optimal levels of concentration and attention; among others, we have the intensity: the higher the level of motivation and intensity that the stimulus exerts on the mind of the human being, then we will have better results in concentration and attention. This combination of neurobiological, social, and pedagogical effects provided by musical activities explains the higher levels of motivation and participation of children observed in the research and reported in the educational-musical literature.

On the other hand, the positive impact found on academic performance is also related to the theories that link music with an improvement of the executive functions necessary for learning in children with ADHD, theories supported, on the one hand, that music activates the brain reward system by releasing dopamine, a neurotransmitter linked to motivation and pleasure, which generates a rewarding effect that would motivate these children to become more involved in the activities and, on the other hand, that social interactions and group work fostered by musical activities increase cohesion among peers and the sense of belonging, facilitating participation [31]; without overlooking that music allows the creative expression of emotions, interests and innate abilities of students, increasing their commitment [32], for the present academic case.

3.2 Proposal for musical-pedagogical intervention

Given the implementation of the proposed activities as a music-pedagogical intervention tool, the results shown in Table 2 were obtained.

Table 2. Results obtained through the implementation of the intervention proposal

Activity	Results
1	The percussion sequences were strengthened, as well as the attention, concentration, impulsiveness, and teamwork of each of the students.
2	The percussion sequences were strengthened, as well as the attention, concentration, impulsiveness, and teamwork of each of the students.
3	The song " <i>Statues</i> " was able to develop the concentration, memory, and attention of the children in a group and individual way in front of the dynamics of the song.
4	With the song <i>Shark Fish</i> , the children strengthened their concentration, memory, and impulsivity through choreography.
5	The children strengthened their attention, memory, and concentration with the rhythm and sequence of the song.
6	The song encouraged the identification of some of the animals and elements that make up planet Earth, helping their attention, memory, and concentration.
7	Students were able to identify the complete sequence of the song " <i>La Tortuguita</i> ", using concentration, memory, and attention as the main elements.
8	It was found that the song helped children's concentration, attention, and memory in the classroom, improving their social and interpersonal behavior.
9	Through the song, the children were able to improve their concentration and memory by recognizing the different types of vegetables, their nutritional functions, and the benefits of their consumption.
10	The children improved their concentration, memory, and attention. This game promoted the development of their musical sensitivity.
11	The children were able to stimulate their concentration to improve their hearing through song.
12	The children improved their concentration, and vocabulary and learned new words related to the <i>pirate song</i> .
13	The children were able to learn the types of emotions and their visual representations, and at the same time, their development of attention, memory, and concentration was encouraged through song.
14	An improvement in the children's social and interpersonal relationships in the classroom was obtained from an improvement in their concentration and attention in front of the musical instruments.
15	Students learned about the sounds of farm and wildlife animals, to improve concentration, attention, emotions, memory, impulsivity, and teamwork.

In line with the results obtained from the methodologies applied to know the effects of music as a pedagogical strategy in children with ADHD in the second grade of a public educational institution, it was

possible to evidence significant findings that support the effectiveness of music as a pedagogical tool to address learning difficulties associated with ADHD.

In general, regarding the improvement in attention and concentration, it was observed that the application of music as a pedagogical tool contributed notoriously and positively to the evaluated population, showing a significant reduction in the episodes of distraction and lack of attention in comparison with the control group, which corresponded to second-grade children without ADHD, these results allow inferring that music favored the maintenance of focus on academic tasks more effectively.

As for impulsivity, music also proved to be effective in reducing it in the ADHD children evaluated. Thus, the participants showed a decrease in impulsive behaviors and a greater reflective capacity before acting in this way. About the above, such improvement in self-control contributed to the establishment of a more orderly school environment and the success of the educational activities implemented during the development of this study.

On the other hand, both motivation and participation on the part of the children who participated in the musical intervention program increased, which was reflected in a greater interest in getting involved in a purposeful way in the classes and performing the assigned tasks, since music acted as an incentive that increased their interest in learning, which translated into a more active participation in class discussions and a greater commitment to the educational process.

One of the most outstanding results was the improvement in the academic performance of the children with ADHD who received the musical intervention since improvements were observed in their grades and in their ability to complete their homework. Likewise, music as a pedagogical tool also positively affected the emotional well-being of the population involved by reducing the levels of anxiety and frustration, contributing to generating healthier relationships and increasing self-esteem among the participants.

The results support the hypothesis that music can be a valuable tool in pedagogical intervention for children with ADHD in the school context, as it proved to be effective not only in improving their attention and concentration, but also in reducing impulsivity and increasing motivation and, in general, in the emotional well-being of the students. These findings have important implications when considering true inclusive education in the case of support for children with special needs.

The action research methodological approach was adequate to understand how music can influence the academic performance and behavior of students with ADHD; likewise, the observation and monitoring of these students allowed the identification of areas in which the musical intervention had a positive impact. At the normative level, it supported the importance of guaranteeing the right to education for all children, including of course those with ADHD. On this issue, national and international laws and regulations emphasize the need to provide quality education that takes into account individual differences.

Regarding the initial diagnosis of the students, which allowed identifying the presence of ADHD in some of them through neuropsychological evaluation, it is appropriate to emphasize the importance of early detection and proper monitoring of students with special needs. Specifically, the first activity, entitled *My Musical Hands*, allowed each student to construct a musical sequence established entirely from their creativity, their hands, the paper musical keys and the values given for each one, for which concentration, memory, attention and control of impulsive actions were required; the latter is consistent with what was proposed by [33], who pointed out that, in addition to bodily discovery, body percussion brings physical and mental well-being, which become evident in the appearance of a better interaction with their environment.

The results of this first pedagogical activity are related to those of the second one, which also included the use of the body to generate musical sounds, allowing greater development of motor coordination, memory, and improved concentration [31]. It should be noted that the execution of this activity had to be repeated so that the participants fully understood the meaning of the activity and developed the required agility; for this purpose, the percussion sequences were elaborated with their bodies at two levels: personal and group, which showed a strengthening, or at least stimulation of working memory, which in children with ADHD can affect processes such as oral comprehension, problem-solving, and temporal organization.

For its part, the activity called *Rhythmic Echoes* favored the control of impulsivity, since it presented a dynamic in which there is a latency period between the external stimulus and the response expected by the students [34]. Similarly, impulsivity control can be worked on using activities that require a delay between the appearance of the external stimulus and the response by the children as, for example, in the case of *Rhythmic Echoes* [24]. On the other hand, the third activity, called *The Statue Game*, was an agent promoting the development of motor activities and the executive functions of attention, concentration, memory, and inhibitory control; this has also been reported by [35].

Additionally, the activities of the songs *El pez tiburón*, *La pelota loca*, and *La Tortuga*, which contained instructions to follow in their lyrics, were useful tools to address the assertive communication favored by the rhythmic sequences. The pedagogical environment enriched by play, art, and expression allowed working on understanding and following instructions, which is consistent with the findings of [36], who shows a positive impact of this type of strategy on the patterns of inappropriate or problematic behaviors frequently presented as a symptom of children with ADHD. Thus, the musical activity favored attention and concentration processes, and, by allowing body mobility and presenting dynamic and moving rhythms, these songs were useful for channeling movement and energy [37].

Regarding the activities called *Musical Chairs* and *The Vegetable Orchestra*, these were presented as an attempt to include all children, regardless of their attention difficulties, with mixed results. Most of the participants were able to enjoy the game and follow the instructions, but five students, mostly with ADHD, had difficulties in the first round, highlighting the persistence of attention problems in certain contexts. However, it is encouraging to note that as the game progressed, some children improved their participation, attention, concentration, and memory, suggesting that inclusion in adapted activities may have a positive effect on these aspects. It also highlights the idea that while inclusion is a positive step towards an equitable educational environment, continued attention and additional strategies are required to ensure the success of all students, especially those with specific difficulties, as mentioned by [38]: *the musical activity provided a valuable opportunity to practice attention and participation skills in a playful and cooperative environment, which could contribute to improvements in the academic performance of children with ADHD.*

In the activities *Orchestra Instruments* and *Conducting and Recognizing Sounds* the results were also encouraging, as the children with ADHD, despite their attention difficulties, showed interest and greater concentration, memory, and enthusiasm in identifying and playing different instruments. This supports the idea that music can be an effective tool for increasing attention and motivation in the educational environment; furthermore, assigning the role of band director to the children provided them with leadership opportunities and fostered mutual respect, resulting in a positive impact on their self-esteem and social skills [39].

The activity called *La pelota loca* fostered coordination, concentration, and social interaction among children, and allowed for better development of their skills, making it a popular choice in children's play environments and activities to assess their development [40].

For their part, the activities entitled *Conociendo mi planeta*, *Canción es emoción* and *La canción del pirata* promoted effective education for children with ADHD, as they combine music, structure, and an important message about environmental protection, appealing to the emotions that each child may have and helping to capture their attention, foster environmental awareness and promote a greater connection with nature while adapting to their specific needs. Music education helps such skills be acquired by promoting students to develop emotions and acquire creativity, as long as they can be accompanied by globalizing and inclusive teaching [41].

During the performance of the *Pirate's Song* activity, there was an increase in interest concerning concentration, memory, and enthusiasm, both in listening and singing, which aided sensory stimulation, as well as an increased focus on adventure, teaching discipline, and ethics, fostering empathy and creating adaptive learning environments. All of these avenues can make the song more effective and engaging for this group of children while providing meaningful learning opportunities.

The *Walking* activity was attractive and beneficial for children with ADHD, as it not only addressed the need to release physical energy but also contributed to the development of essential cognitive, emotional, and social skills, therefore, by incorporating walking creatively in play and learning environments, it is a valuable tool for their integral development and wellbeing. Additionally, with this activity it was possible to make use of multiple intelligences; therefore, it is important to work on them in the early childhood education stage, since this is when children develop their personality, foster their learning bases, and are at a time when they can train and perfect the learning processes in which they present difficulties [20].

The *Farm* activity provided valuable insight into how children challenged by ADHD interact with everyday concepts and environments, providing insight into how they understand what a farm and its wildlife represent. In addition, they demonstrated an ability to identify and reproduce animal sounds, indicating their cognitive and auditory perceptual abilities. These findings are important in the context of the implementation of music-based pedagogical strategies for children with ADHD, as they show that children can actively participate in activities related to music and learning and, at the same time, that music, as a pedagogical tool, can take advantage of children's ability to identify sounds and express themselves creatively.

Recapitulating the above, all these musical activities seem to have a positive impact on the participation and social skills of children with ADHD, which may contribute to their academic improvement by fostering a more inclusive and motivating learning environment; as for pedagogical strategies based on music and participation, they are effective in engaging children with ADHD in learning, improving their ability to concentrate and their participation in group activities. However, further research is needed to have a greater body of knowledge, both theoretical and practical, to evaluate the impact of these strategies on long-term academic performance and to adapt them in a relevant way so that they can address the individual requirements of children.

In summary, the present study demonstrates that music plays a significant role in improving the attention, concentration, impulsivity, motivation, academic performance, and emotional well-being of children with ADHD in an educational setting. The results further suggest that the integration of music-based pedagogical strategies can be an effective practice, both in addressing the learning difficulties associated with ADHD and in improving their educational experience. Further research is recommended to further validate these findings and to delve into the specific mechanisms through which music exerts its positive influence on this population; future research may contribute to a more comprehensive and effective perspective on the education of children with ADHD.

4. CONCLUSIONS

Students with ADHD in second grade at José Joaquín Flórez Hernández High School face difficulties in the transcription of information, concentration, task completion, and behavior, which affects their academic performance and classroom dynamics.

There is a lack of attention to ADHD in the educational context of Ibagué, which translates into a lack of adequate pedagogical strategies, creating weaknesses in terms of inclusion and equity.

Interventions based on musical strategies have shown positive results in the management of ADHD in school environments, so music as a pedagogical tool could improve the performance of students with ADHD, being a promising alternative and complementary to traditional treatments, mostly pharmacological.

A musical pedagogical proposal of active workshops was designed and implemented for six weeks to intervene second-grade students with ADHD at José Joaquín Flórez Hernández High School, seeking to strengthen cognitive and behavioral functions affected by this disorder. This proposal was based on a previous diagnostic evaluation of skills, focusing the activities on the specific needs of students with ADHD, and achieved its specific objective.

The implementation of the pedagogical-musical proposal achieved improvements in attention, concentration, impulse control, and motivation of students with ADHD compared to the control group.

Participants also experienced a reduction in disruptive behaviors, a greater ability to complete tasks, and increased academic performance, as well as a decrease in anxiety and frustration.

The positive effects support the premise of the incorporation of music as a valuable tool in the educational intervention for children with ADHD, in this regard it is important to highlight the role of teachers and the need for adequate teacher training that allows them to adapt this type of strategies to the individual needs of the students. Finally, although the specific objectives were met, further research is needed to deepen the results found.

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